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Building and Enhancing New Literacies

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To further understand what "new literacy" is, we must first talk about the concept of literacy. The simplest definition of literacy is the capacity for reading and writing. The process of being more literate involves learning more about reading and writing in order to think more critically and acquire knowledge that will help one better comprehend the world and oneself. In order to help people fulfill their potential, reach their goals, and fully engage in their community, literacy entails a continuum of learning (UNESCO, 2004; 2017).

Over time, the definition of literacy has changed. Literacy has evolved from being defined as just "the ability to read and write" to include other abilities necessary to function in today's fast-paced society. The traditional literacy refers to the capacity to interpret and make sense of words, images, and other materials that a reader may put together to comprehend.

There is much more to the new literacies. Their use is for reading on the internet. The Internet and other information and communication technologies demand understanding and learning abilities, often known as 21st century skills, for content available on wikis, blogs, video sites, audio sites, and e-mail. Students also need to be able to use the Internet, locate information, evaluate it critically, synthesize it, and communicate.

The emergence of "new literacies" due to technology includes texting, blogging, social networking, podcasting, and video production. These digital technologies, which usually integrate text, music, and visual, change and increase our ability to communicate. These technologies alter the definition of "read," even while they are linked to more traditional, "offline" methods and "write" written works.

Digital natives may be tech aware, but that doesn't mean they use a lot of information or, at the very least, they don't know how to evaluate the information they do. They require direction on where to look for the best information quickly and how to distinguish fact from fiction.

Teachers need to consider and elaborate on the idea of what literacy skills learner require to flourish in this contemporary environment, aside from the evident changes in literacy materials over the last few decades. Digital multi-literate technologies need for additional abilities like semantic comprehension, skills related to management, networking, and assessment. According to Edwards-Groves (2012), digital literacies do not supplant fundamental writing and reading skills; rather, they expand upon them to accommodate the change in teaching methods that technology facilitates.

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We must develop multi-literate digital classrooms that integrate both traditional and new age literacy teaching methods in order to give our learners the finest learning environment possible. A learner's early exposure to adult discussion, engagement, and mentoring is the single most critical factor in determining their future performance in reading and content acquisition in school. As educators, we must embrace multi-literacies and be aware of the ongoing shift in literacies in order to create a highly productive atmosphere.

Reference:

Sanders, A. 2016. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/new-literacies>.

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